

Information technologies in teaching a foreign language

Ochilova Madina

Chirchik State Pedagogical University

(Supervisor: Elmurodov Ulugbek)

Annotation. The following article deals with development of education, which organically linked with an increase in the level of its information potential. This characteristic feature largely determines both the direction of the evolution of education itself and the future of the whole society. For the most successful orientation in the global information space, it is necessary for students to master information culture, as well as computer-screen culture, since the Internet is increasingly given priority in the search for information. The creation of the Internet, or World Wide Web, has become one of the most revolutionary achievements of the last decades, affecting the educational process on a global scale.

Key words: choice of techniques, speech activity, age-related psychological characteristics, low-grade information products

The use of Internet technologies is a new direction of general didactics and private methodology, as the ongoing changes affect all aspects of the educational process, from the choice of techniques and work style to changing requirements for the academic level of students.

The basis for the use of telecommunication capabilities in teaching a foreign language is that they not only represent an effective means of optimizing the conditions of intellectual labor in general, in any of its manifestations, but also offer a wide range of opportunities for the development of speech activity in all its directions: listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

The language learning process is aimed at forming students' communicative competence, the ability to freely express their thoughts on any topic of interest to them, to take part in a conversation, discussion – whether written or oral communication; to vary the structure and style of utterance depending on the social characteristics of communication. In this sense, the Internet fully meets the tasks of language teaching, since it itself is primarily a means of communication and live situational communication. The Internet allows not only simulating a communication situation in the classroom, but also offers a lively and relevant dialogue with native speakers and representatives of other cultures.

Communicating in a true language environment provided by the Internet, students find themselves in authentic life situations. Involved in solving a wide range of significant, realistic, interesting and achievable tasks, schoolchildren learn to

respond spontaneously and adequately to them, which stimulates, instead of template manipulation of language formulas, the creation of original statements.

Often, the teacher faces the problem of finding authentic, modern and interesting information for students on the topics provided in the curriculum. This problem can also be solved with the help of the Internet, which is not only a means of communication, but also the most extensive information resource.

As an information system, the Internet offers its users a variety of information and resources. A standard set of services provided on the World Wide Web:

- * E-mail (e-mail);
- * Reference directories (Yahoo!, InfoSeek/UltraSmart, LookSmart, Galaxy);
- * Search engines (Alta Vista, HotBob, Open Text, WebCrawler, Excite, and such well-known Russian search engines as Yandex, Rambler);
- * Echo conferences (message boards);
- * Teleconferences (usenet);
- * Video conferences;
- * Access to news and information resources;
- * Online conversation (Chat) – text and voice.
- * The ability to publish your own information, create your own homepage and place it on a Web server:

All these possibilities, which are composed of the Internet, can be successfully used in the lesson.

The use of Internet resources in a foreign language lesson in terms of mastering communicative and intercultural competence, which is impossible without the practice of communication, is simply irreplaceable: the virtual environment of the Internet allows you to go beyond the time and spatial framework, giving its users the opportunity to communicate authentic with real interlocutors on topics relevant to both sides. However, we must not forget that the Internet is only an auxiliary technical means of teaching, and in order to achieve optimal results, it is necessary to competently integrate its use into the lesson process.

Some possible difficulties when using the Internet.

First of all, it is necessary to remember that the Internet is only an auxiliary technical means of teaching, and in order to achieve optimal results, it is necessary to competently integrate its use into the lesson process. The use of Internet resources in teaching in the absence of a methodological basis cannot be successful or useful.

The Internet is accessible and rich in resources, but these advantages are also a source of problems: an almost unlimited amount of unstructured information

significantly complicates the search for the necessary material, and the lack of control over the quality and content of documents placed in the virtual space leads to the appearance (along with high-quality materials prepared by professionals) of low-grade information products. It is difficult to cope with these problems even for experienced Internet users, while newcomers spend a lot of time and relatively low search results form a stable belief in the advantage of traditional methods of education.

The only way out in such a situation is to increase the computer literacy of the teacher, first of all – the development of the skill of using search engines (IPS).

The most reasonable search strategy is to choose two or three well-known and well-proven IPS and learn how to use them effectively. IPS can be classified by the type of information they find on general and special purpose IPS. Special purpose IPS include, for example, Ditto (<http://www.ditto.com/>) and StreamSearch.com (<http://www.streamsearch.com/music/home.asp>), specializing in the search for graphic, audio, video and multimedia materials on the World Wide Web; Daypop (<http://www.daypop.com>), which searches for news; Topica (<http://www.topica.com/dir/?cid=0>) and Publicly Accessible Mailing Lists (<http://paml.net>), indispensable when searching for teleconferences, mailing lists, discussion groups; Complete Planet (<http://www.completeplanet.com/>), InvisibleWeb.com (<http://www.invisibleweb.com>), which open access to the resources of the “invisible Network”, etc. general-purpose IPS are such well-known systems as Yahoo!, AltaVista, Google or Go.com. They are perfect for even a novice user. Each of these sites has a detailed description of the virtual resource search methodology, which should be carefully read before starting the search.

Conclusion

The use of telecommunication technologies also implies providing students with a greater share of independence, which is especially important, for example, at the middle and senior stages of learning English, when, in accordance with age-related psychological characteristics, students increasingly need partial independence from the teacher. The use of the Internet, in addition, in many cases is closely related to the method of project work (for example, the creation of presentations, websites based on the material typed on the web on a given topic), which provides an opportunity for creative self-expression. Thus, another important aspect of using computer technology in a foreign language lesson is creating a favorable socio-psychological atmosphere and maintaining motivation to learn a foreign language.

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